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Chemical Recycling of Amine Cured Epoxy Resin Using Nitric Acid

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SUMMARY: Bisphenol F type epoxy resin cured with 1,8-p-menthane diamine had low corrosion resistance to strong inorganic acid solutions, especially in nitric acid solution it could be completely decomposed in short immersion time. By considering the corrosion phenomena, chemical recycling method was proposed. Organic decomposed products of the resin in nitric acid were extracted from neutralized environment. The extractive was used to make recycled resin by adding it into epoxy resin and being cured with phthalic anhydride. The mechanical properties of neat and recycled resins were compared, and among them the recycled resin containing 25% extractive showed the highest flexural strength. Furthermore, The results of differential scanning calorimeter (DSC) showed the glass transition temperature of recycled resins was higher than neat resin due to the recycled resins having better network structure.

KEYWORDS: Recycling, Epoxy resin, Decomposition

INTRODUCTION

Fiber reinforced plastics (FRP) have been widely used in many fields due to their excellent mechanical properties and durability.¹ However, because thermosetting resins, matrices of FRP, can neither be remelted nor dissolved into ordinary solvent, arising from their network structure, it is difficult to dispose of or reuse them, causing many environmental problems.²⁻³ Although many approaches to polymer waste disposal have been already explored, including source reduction, thermal recovering, recycling and so on, landfill is still a main way to dispose of thermosetting resins by now. Consequently, technologies of polymer recycling urgently need to be improved and developed.⁴⁻⁵ In recent years, the chemical recycling of waste polymers has received a great deal of attention.⁶⁻⁷

We have been investigating the corrosion resistance of amine cured epoxy resin, finding that it had low resistance to acid solution,⁸ and was decomposed if the concentration of acid

was high.⁹ This phenomena suggested the possibility of recycling thermosetting resins by using their decomposed products.

The decomposition of typical epoxy resin, bisphenol A type epoxy resin cured with amine, in acid solution has been studied.¹⁰ Since it was very easy to be corroded, it was intended to apply to chemical recycling. However, it is found that bisphenol A was easy to break its main chain, because A type possessed quaternary carbon atom, which was susceptible to be attacked by acid to produce tertiary positive ion. As a result, it was difficult to retain the structure of main chain in strong inorganic acid, and therefore not easy to be re-polymerized.

This paper was focusing on bisphenol F type epoxy resin that possessed $-CH_2-$ in the center of main chain. The objectives of the paper were: to investigate the decomposition mechanism of epoxy resin cured with amine in nitric acid solution; and to propose the recycling method of re-polymerizing the decomposed products with original resin.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

Bisphenol F type epoxy resin (R110) and curing agent, 1,8-p-menthane diamine (MDA), were used in the work. In addition, phthalic anhydride (PA) was used as curing agent when the decomposed products were recycled. See *Figure 1* for their chemical structure.

Figure 1 Chemical structural formulae of epoxy resin and curing agent.

Decomposition Experiments

Epoxy resin was cured with MDA (BF/MDA) in weight ratio of 100:22 at 80. for 2h, and then the post-curing was conducted at 150. for 3h. The BF/MDA was cast to 2 mm thick plate and then cut into 25 mm wide and 60 mm long pieces. The specimens fixed by support bars of Teflon were put into 30 mm diameter glass tubes, then immersed in 70 ml of 4mol/l and 6mol/l nitric acid solution respectively, as depicted in *Figure 2*. The temperature was controlled at 80. in the water bath.

It was observed that yellowish brown decomposed compound with high viscosity, namely “residue” (RE), appeared in the upper and bottom of solution. After the residue and remaining specimens were removed from the solution, needle shaped crystal (CR) was recovered by being cooled in ice water in the case that 6mol/l nitric acid solution was used. In the case of 4mol/l solution, no crystal appeared. Finally, by adding ethyl acetate into the yellow solution where the needle crystal had been removed if it existed, brown high-viscosity product was extracted, referred to as “extractive” (EX).

Figure 2 Schematic illustration of corrosion behavior of epoxy resin in acid solution.

Procedure of neutralizing extractive

In order to neutralize nitric acid contained in EX, it was dissolved in ethyl acetate, and specified amount of sodium carbonate solution was poured into the solution, with stirring. When pH of the mixture solution reached 7, neutralized EX was separated from the solution. It was then dried under room temperature at least for one day. Because water can partly dissolve into ethyl acetate, neutralized EX contained sodium nitrate. To remove the inorganic compounds, the neutralized EX was redissolved in ethyl acetate again, and then filtered and separated. At last it was dried in vacuum under room temperature, named neutralized extractive (NT-EX).

Re-polymerization of neutralized extractive

Initially, solvent removal and preheating was carried out at 80. for about 1h. And then weighed epoxy resin (R110), NT-EX, and PA were mixed. After degassing and solvent removal in vacuum oven at 115., the mixture was cast. The curing reaction was carried out at 115. for 8h, and post-curing at 130. for 10h, and then recycled resin was produced.

Analytical methods

Size exclusion chromatograph (SEC) was applied to determine the molecular weight distributions of RE, EX and CR. Tetrahydrofuran (THF) was used as mobile phase and the flow rate was maintained at 0.1ml/min . FT-IR was applied to analyze their chemical

structures.

In addition, strength of recycled resin and neat resin was measured (20.) by the three-point bending experiment. Their fracture surfaces were analyzed by scanning electron microscope (SEM). Differential scanning calorimeter (DSC) was performed at a heating rate of 5./min to determine the glass transition temperature (Tg) of neat resin and recycled resins.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Yields of the decomposed products

Figure 3 gives the change of yield of each decomposed product with immersion time in 4mol/l nitric acid solution. It can be seen that the resin was rapidly decomposed, and completely disappeared at the immersion time of about 100h. RE and EX appeared at the beginning of immersion, and increased gradually. The yields of RE and EX started to reduce after they reached their highest levels, respectively, at 50 hours for RE, and at 150 hours for EX after the resin was totally decomposed, being 60wt% of initial resin. CR did not appear under this condition. For the case of 6mol/l solution, CR appeared after 150 hours, then it increased gradually to reach the largest yield of 25%.

Figure 3 Change of yields with BF/MDA decomposed in 4mol/l nitric acid solution.

Analysis of decomposed products

At first CR was analyzed. From the curve of SEC of CR, only a unique peak could be observed, as led to assume that CR was a pure compound. The analysis of the Gas Chromatograph-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) provided the molecular weight of CR was 229. It implied that when the cured resin was deeply decomposed, the main chain was broken, and the low molecular weight aromatic compound was produced. From the structure of original material, it was predicted that CR could be 2,4,6-trinitrophenol (picric acid), whose molecular weight is 229.11. To further confirm this, the spectra of CR and picric acid obtained from FT-IR were compared in Figure 4. Note that CR and picric acid had almost the same absorption spectra, as confirmed that the principle ingredient of CR was picric acid. Due to

the breakage of main chain and subsequent nitric acid, picric acid was produced and the reaction scheme is given in *Figure 5*.

Figure 4 FT-IR spectra of picric acid and CR for BF/MDA decomposed by nitric acid.

Figure 5 Mechanism and schematic process for production of picric acid (CR).

By analyzing the SEC result of RE, molecular weight peaks were found to during distribute from low to high region, suggesting that RE was mixture of intermediate products decomposition process of resin and curing agent.

FT-IR spectra of original resin and EX are compared in *Figure 6*. The peak at 1350 cm^{-1} in the IR region of EX corresponded to nitro compound. Aromatic nitro groups absorbing strongly at 1540 cm^{-1} were also found in the IR spectrum of EX. The results demonstrated that the original resin was nitrified. Furthermore, the peaks of aliphatic ether groups at 1110 cm^{-1} and aromatic ether groups at 1040 cm^{-1} appearing in spectrum of the original resin almost disappeared in that of EX, implying that the ether bonds between and within the molecules were modified due to the effect of the nitric acid. Finally, from the molecular weight distribution of EX, shown in *Figure 7*, it was found that the peaks appearing in high molecular region moved to low molecular region with increase of immersion time. It was

supposed that EX was mixture with lower molecular weight compounds. Based on these findings and the structure of the original material, it was concluded that EX was the nitrified mixture that retained the structure of main chain of original bisphenol resin. Because the main chain was not broken in EX, we considered that it could be reused as quasi-monomer for recycling the resin.

Figure 6 FT-IR spectra of BF/MDA resin and decomposed products EX: (a) BF/MDA resin before immersion; (b) EX immersed for 150h.

Figure 7 Change of molecular weight distribution of EX for BF/MDA decomposed in 4mol/l nitric acid solution.

RECYCLING METHODS

On the basis of above discussions, two basic methods of recycling epoxy resin were proposed and described as follows.

Crystal recovering

BF/MDA could be recycled by collecting the crystal (CR), i.e. picric acid, after complete

decomposition. If the concentration of acid was higher and the immersion time was longer, it was easier to obtain picric acid with high purity and yield. It is known that picric acid is widely applied in medical chemicals, agricultural chemicals, dyes, gunpowder and so on.¹¹

The method is easy to apply, especially for those resins having low resistance to nitric acid. It can also be used in the chemical recycling of other thermosetting resins containing benzene ring or mixture of several of those resins.

Monomer chemical recycling

As presented before, BF/MDA could also be recycled by using the decomposed compounds whose main chains were retained. By controlling the immersion conditions, the reaction was stopped before the main chains were broken down. Then the quasi-monomer retaining structure of original resin was obtained by extraction. After further chemical treatment, the extractive was used to remold together with original epoxy resin (R110) and curing agent of PA.

Decomposed product, EX, obtained at 150h immersion time was selected as recycling material because its yield was highest (see *figure 2*). The neutralized extractive (NT-EX) was added into epoxy resin (R110) in various weight ratios: 0 (BF/PA), 5, 10, 15, 20, 25 and 30%. After the mixture was cured with phthalic anhydride (PA), a cast plate of 2mm thickness was prepared.

At the 30% adding level, cured resin could not be moulded because of its high viscosity and short pot life. *Figure 8* shows the photo of moulded recycled resin containing 30% of NT-EX. There were many bubbles in resin sample, which were formed in the process of degassing under vacuum. The reaction was so rapid that gas was prevented from escaping out of the viscous resin. On the other hand, below 25%, casting was perfectly done, and 2mm thick recycled resin plates without any bubble could be obtained.

The flexural strength was evaluated from the three-point bending test and is shown in *Table 1*. The flexural strength of recycled resin containing 5% NT-EX was almost the same

Figure 8 Photo of recycled resin containing 30% NT-EX.

as the cured neat epoxy resin. When the content of NT-EX was from 5% to 25%, the flexural strength increased, reaching its highest point at 25% level.

The curing reaction of acid anhydride can be accelerated if the Lewis base exists, which acts as initiator to the reaction.¹² The NT-EX might contain tertiary amine that acts as the Lewis base, as resulted in the curing reaction of recycled resin was faster than that of neat resin. Therefore, it was considered that because of the existence of tertiary amine, the recycled resin formed the higher density network than the neat resin under the same reaction conditions.

Table 1 Flexural strength of neat resin and recycled resins with the change of content of NT-EX.

Content of NT-EX (wt%)	Flexural Strength (MPa)
0% (neat resin)	116.3
5%	115.9
10%	136.4
15%	134.6
20%	142.6
25%	147.5

In order to confirm the fracture mechanism of recycled resin, the fracture surfaces of the three-point bending test specimens were observed by SEM. The fracture surface of neat BF/PA is shown in *Figure 9a*. The surface was flat and smooth, and the size of initial crack was large, as correlated with its lower flexural strength. The fracture surface shown in *Figure 9b* is for recycled resin containing 25% NT-EX. The surface was relatively rough, and the size of initial crack was smaller than that of neat resin. This observation could account for its higher flexural strength of recycled resin.

In addition, it was observed that the sample of recycled resin was uniform and had no significant defect, implying that epoxy resin, NT-EX, and PA reacted and produced the new resin with good network structure.

Furthermore, recycled resins were compared with neat resin by means of DSC analysis. The analytical results are shown in *Figure 10*, where each of them had one peak in the range of the temperature. This provided additional evidence that epoxy resin, NT-EX, and PA reacted and formed uniform structure. Also, the glass transition temperature of recycled resins was higher than that of neat resin and increased with increasing of the content of NT-EX. The increase of T_g suggested that, as hoped, the addition of NT-EX not only did not interfere in epoxy resin-PA reaction but also the density of cross-link in recycled resin increased. It was because recycled resin had better network structure than neat resin that recycled one showed higher flexural strength.

Figure 9 SEM photographs of fracture surfaces: (a) neat resin-BF/PA; (b) recycled resin containing 25% NT-EX.

Figure 10 DSC scans of recycled resins in comparison with neat resin: (a) neat resin; (b) recycled resin containing 10% NT-EX; (c) recycled resin containing 25% NT-EX.

CONCLUSIONS

Bisphenol F type epoxy resin cured with 1,8-p-menthane diamine could be decomposed by nitric acid. The decomposition mechanism was analyzed, and the recycling methods were proposed. The conclusions can be drawn as follows:

(1) Bisphenol F type epoxy resin cured with 1,8-p-menthane diamine was decomposed by nitric acid to produce three kinds of decomposed products, including residue, crystal and extractive. The crystal was proved to be 2,4,6-trinitrophenol (picric acid) resulting from breakage of the main chain and subsequent nitration. The residue was an intermediate product during the decomposition process, and the extractive was mainly a nitrified mixture retaining the structure of main chain, equivalent to monomer or dimer.

(2) When the concentration of nitric acid was high and immersion time was long, picric acid of high purity may be obtained. This gave a method of recycling thermosetting resin containing benzene rings.

(3) The neutralized extractive was used to make recycled resin by adding it into epoxy resin,

and being cured with phthalic anhydride (PA). Recycled resin with uniform structure was prepared by reaction of the mixture.

(4) The mechanical properties of recycled resin were reported. The recycled resin containing 25% extractive showed the highest flexural strength. Under the condition considered, the flexural strength of recycled resin was higher than that of neat resin. Glass transition temperature of recycled resins was higher than that of neat resin and increased with increasing the content of NT-EX.

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